

THE EFFECTS OF THERMOPLASTIC FILM-INTERLEAVING ON STIFFNESS LOSS DUE TO MATRIX CRACKING AND SUBSEQUENT DELAMINATION IN COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

The effects of incorporating ductile thermoplastic films at delamination prone $-30/90$ and $+30/-30$ interfaces of $[\pm 30/90]_n$ laminates have been investigated for $n = 1$ and 2 , respectively. Results showed that the constraining effects of the ± 30 plies on transverse ply cracking were not affected by the presence of the relatively low modulus films. Interleaving in fact delayed transverse cracking which significantly reduced the stiffness loss. Delamination onset stress was raised with interleaving except for the $[\pm 30/L/90]$ laminate where $L/90$ edge delamination was the first failure mode. Delamination growth in all the interleaved laminates was not uniform resulting in pockets of delamination zones. SEM examination showed that because of good film/composite bonding, delaminations at the interleaved interfaces were cohesive failures, where interply debonding occurred at least 3 fibre spaces away from the interleave edge.

INTRODUCTION

The use of interleaving techniques for toughening the inter-layers of thermosetting based composite materials is gaining acceptance. This is because the method involves only a minor modification to the laminate construction and does not require changes to existing processing techniques. The concept of interleaving, as first introduced in 1986 by Chan [1], consists of inserting tough, ductile layers of resin between the relatively more brittle composite plies to reduce interply delamination. Later work [2] found that interleaves were only necessary at delamination-prone interfaces. Selective interleaving and minimizing the interleaving layer thickness also helped to reduce losses in in-plane strength and modulus of the modified composite.

The early work in interleaving used commercial thermoset-based film adhesives (e.g. FM 300) as the interleaving material [2,3], but recent studies have found thermoplastic films to be more effective if there was good film/composite ply bonding [4,5]. This was attributed to the higher transverse strain capability (expansion) offered by thermoplastic films at the thin region between the rigid composite plies. It became evident then that the interleaving film is effective only as long as the plastic zone size of the delamination crack was less than the film thickness [5].

In a previous paper [6], a ductile thermoplastic film with low glass transition (T_g) was found to improve the interlaminar shear strength and Mode I fracture toughness of glass/epoxy laminates. Much of the improvement was attributed to the significantly higher failure strain of the film and good adhesion at the film/composite interface due to similar T_g values.

The present paper is a further development which investigates the effects of selective film interleaving on the progressive damage behaviour of $[\pm 30/90_n]_s$ laminates. This stacking sequence results in a relatively high tensile interlaminar normal stress (σ_{zz}) at the -30/90 and somewhat lower interlaminar shear stress (τ_{xz}) at the -30/+30 free-edges, respectively. When the laminates are loaded in tension along the longitudinal laminate axis, matrix cracking in the transverse plies is assumed to be the first damage mode observed and multiplies with increasing applied load until the characteristic damage state (CDS) is reached [7]. Subsequently, either edge delamination will form between the -30/90 interface or local delamination will initiate from the transverse ply cracks tips due to high local stresses.

All the failure processes namely, matrix cracking, edge and local delaminations cause redistribution of the stresses among the plies within the laminate resulting in a reduction of stiffness and strength. The present work aims to determine the effects of interleaving at each of the delamination prone interfaces on transverse cracking and delamination damage, using stiffness reduction to compare the magnitude of damage.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

SPECIMEN PREPARATION

The materials used for composite preparation were E-glass fibres and Chemcrete R-14 epoxy resin, a hot curing diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA). Unidirectional prepreg tape was produced using a Research Tool Corporation Model 40 laboratory scale prepregging machine. The wet prepreg was cut and hand laid-up to construct laminates with $[\pm 30/90_n]_s$ stacking sequence where $n=1$ and 2. Altogether, three sets of laminates were fabricated: (i) baseline laminates with no interleaving; (ii) laminates interleaved at the +30/-30 interfaces; and (iii) laminates interleaved at -30/90 interfaces.

The interleaving material consisted of a 0.1 mm thermoplastic film which was found to be effective in previous work [6]. The films were inserted during the lay-up stage, vacuum bagged and then co-cured at 140°C in a hot press under 5 bar pressure and full vacuum for 5 hours. All laminates were further post-cured in a vacuum oven for 9 hours at 120°C. The fibre volume fractions were measured by burning off the epoxy in a thermogravimetric analyzer. Two test coupons having dimensions 23 cm length x 2.5 cm width were cut from the center region of each laminate panel using a water-cooled diamond cut-off saw. The coupon edges were then ground with 180 grit silicon carbide paper to ensure relatively smooth surfaces. Fibreglass tabs of length 3.75 cm were bonded to each coupon.

TENSILE TESTING AND DELAMINATION MEASUREMENT

Incremental tensile testing was conducted on each coupon using an Instron testing machine at a constant cross-head speed of 0.5 mm/min. A 5-cm averaging extensometer was used to measure axial strain and the stiffness was calculated from load-strain data for each load increment of about 1 kN. As soon as edge delamination occurred, the coupon was unloaded to record the laminate stiffness. For consistency, all the stiffness values were based on the tangent modulus for the initial 0.05% strain of the stress-strain curve.

Transverse matrix cracking damage was observed to precede delamination but was not measured. The extent of transverse cracking was estimated based on the stiffness loss before delamination onset. It was observed in preliminary tests that delamination was not accompanied by matrix cracking in the +30 and -30 plies. The delamination size was measured by mapping the delamination profile in-situ using a rigid transparent film. This was possible as the delaminated areas were easily distinguishable as "white zones" when a bright is focused from the sides of the thin specimens. The location of the delaminated interfaces were checked for the thicker specimens (n=2) by inspecting the edges with a travelling microscope. For convenience, the delaminated width rather than the area was measured off the profiles since they were found to be linearly related. Two sets of incremental tests were performed for each lay-up. The second coupon were loaded up to 80% of the fracture load in order to conduct post-fracture microscopy.

Post-fracture specimen preparation involved cutting off a 25 mm length from the center region with a diamond cut-off saw and then sectioning the square specimen lengthwise into 6 slices. Each slice was then cold mounted and polished using cerium oxide slurry. The polished edges were then observed using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) and photographed to measure transverse crack spacing and to document the location of delamination fracture.

RESULTS

The elastic material constants, strength constants and other relevant properties for composite lamina and interleaving film are shown in Table 1. The initial elastic modulus E_x^o from test results are compared with Laminate Plate Theory predictions in columns 3 and 4 of Table 2. The LPT calculations which accounts for the presence of low modulus interleaving film are in good agreement with the test results. Calculated volume fractions of interleaving film for each laminate are shown in column 2. The average strains at which the onset of transverse cracking (ϵ_t^{min}) and delamination (ϵ_D^o) were observed are tabulated in columns 6 and 7. The ϵ_t^{min} values were based on the "knee" in the stress-strain curves, while ϵ_D^o was estimated by dividing the measured onset stress (σ_D^o) by the laminate reduced modulus. As suggested by Ref. [3], the nominal thickness of the glass-epoxy was used to calculate the onset stress since the low modulus interleave carries a very small portion of the load. The corresponding values of ϵ_t^{min} predicted using Parvizi *et al.*'s shear-lag theory [8] are shown in column 5.

STIFFNESS REDUCTION AND OBSERVED DAMAGE

The magnitude of stiffness reduction due to transverse cracking ($a_D = 0$) is tabulated for all the laminates in column 9 of Table 2. The subsequent stiffness drop due to delamination width of 20 mm ($a_D = 20$) is tabulated in column 10. In the last column, the total stiffness loss due to accumulated damage up to $a_D = 20$ mm is shown. The same results are plotted in Figure 1.

The method for post-fracture examination of the second set of coupons (loaded up to 80% maximum load) is schematically shown in Figure 2. Each section is identified by letters A,B., and so on. Figure 3 shows typical delamination patterns observed in the interleaved specimens in the early stages of delamination growth. Details of delaminated interfaces are shown in Figure 4. For clarity, only transverse cracks related to local delaminations were drawn. As expected, the crack spacings in the baseline laminates were about the width of the 90° ply. Transverse cracking was observed to be the first failure mode in the interleaved laminates where the range of crack spacings at 80% load were: 0.63-2.7 mm for [+30/L/-30/90]_s; 0.7-1.2 mm for [+30/L/-30/90]_{2s}; and 0.7-1.8 mm for [\pm 30/L/90]_{2s}. Transverse cracks were minimal in the [\pm 30/L/90]_s laminate where edge delamination was the first failure mode.

Table 1. Typical properties of composite lamina and interleaving film.

Material	Thickness (mm)	T _g (°C)	Elastic parameters				Strength parameters			
			E ₁₁ (GPa)	E ₂₂ (GPa)	G ₁₂ (GPa)	ν ₁₂	σ ₁ (MPa)	σ ₂ (MPa)	ε ₁ ^u (%)	ε ₂ ^u (%)
E-glass/epoxy	0.25	87.4*	54.0	8.86	7.66	0.26	1063	14	1.97	0.158
Interleave film	0.1	78.8	2.47	2.47	0.95	0.3	53	53	109.4	109.4

*before post-curing

Table 2. Summary of experimental results from tension tests.

Lay-up	V _{interleave}	E _x ^o LPT	E _x ^o Expt.	ε ^{min} _t (%) Pred.	ε ^{min} _t (%) Expt.	ε ^o (%) Calc.	σ ^o _D a _D =0	ΔE _x (%) a _D =0	ΔE _x (%) a _D =20	TOTAL ΔE _x (%)
[±30/90] _s	0	27.98	27.60	0.0687	0.075	0.356	79.6	17	18	35
[30/L/-30/90] _s	0.126	23.89	24.13	0.0687	0.073	0.42	100.6	7.3	15.5	22.8
[±30/L/90] _s	0.125	23.89	23.90	0.0687	undetected	0.3	71.5	1.7	12.3	14
[±30/90] _{2s}	0	22.71	23.55	0.048	0.05	0.34	52.6	35	15	50
[+30/L/-30/90] _{2s}	0.114	20.11	20.94	0.048	0.05	0.33	61.5	11	16	27
[±30/L/90] _{2s}	0.112	19.93	20.05	0.048	0.0455	0.39	64.2	1.8	14	15.8

E_x^o, σ^o_D, ε^{min}_t(%), ΔE_x(%) are the average of two tests.

Figure 1. Normalised stiffness as a function of delamination width for all laminates.

Figure 2. Procedure used to section second coupon for SEM examination.

Figure 3. Schematic showing typical delamination pattern in interleaved laminates.

Fig 4. Sections of interleaved laminates after testing to 80% maximum load.

Fig 5. SEM micrograph of interply delamination.

Fig.6. Damage near interleave.

DISCUSSION

Interleaved [30/L/-30/90]_n, Laminates Failure

For baseline laminates where $n=1$, transverse cracking in the thin 90° mid-ply resulted in a stiffness loss of about 17% on reaching the CDS. The incorporation of film interleaves at the $+30/-30$ interface reduced the extent of transverse cracking even at relatively high stresses and the crack density did not reach saturation. Correspondingly, the stiffness loss was significantly reduced to less than half (7.3%). A similar behaviour was also seen for $n=2$ although the stiffness loss was not as great. Such behaviour was not expected since the introduction of the low modulus film should in fact reduce the constraining effects of the outer ± 30 plies [9].

Interleaved [$\pm 30/L/90$]_n, Laminates Failure

For $n=1$, the onset of edge delamination at the $L/90$ interfaces was the first damage mode. Based on the negligible stiffness loss, there was minimal transverse cracking prior to delamination. This was confirmed in the SEM sections where transverse cracks were hardly noticeable even at 80% maximum load. Consistent with the results of Ref. [2], transverse cracking was suppressed when the mid-ply was sandwiched between the film interleaves.

There was limited edge delamination growth after initiation. Initial edge delaminations did not spread uniformly across the specimen width with increasing load as reported by [2]. Rather, new delaminations were initiated along the edge, as shown in Figure 3. Even close to the laminate failure strain, the delaminations appeared to have been arrested and new delaminations formed across the laminate width. Final failure was triggered by edge delamination at the $-30/30$ interface and fracture of the interleaving film.

For $n=2$, primary delamination was shifted to the $L/-30$ interface. SEM examination showed that the delamination cracks typically propagated as a cohesive-type failure within the -30 layer at about 2-3 fibre spaces away from the interleave edge (Fig. 5). The bonding between the film interleave and -30 layer remained unaffected. Moreover, transverse cracking in the 90° mid-ply and interply failure seemed to be independent events separated by the interleaving film, implying that the crack tips did not trigger the onset of local delamination. Transverse crack tips which penetrated the interleave film tend to terminate within this ductile region, Fig.6.

Stiffness Loss and Delamination Growth Pattern

For the relatively thin laminates tested, the overall magnitude of stiffness loss due delamination for both methods of interleaving did not vary significantly from the baseline materials. According to O'Brien's edge delamination model and sublaminates theory [10], the resultant stiffness of partially delaminated specimens can be estimated from the delamination size and sublaminates stiffnesses. The present work did not perform the calculations because the delamination growth pattern was scattered and it not was evident if delamination was always occurring at the same interfaces. Nevertheless, the present results imply that the same sublaminates were formed even when interleaves were present. The advantage of interleaving however was seen in the higher delamination onset stress.

The scattered delamination pattern in the [$\pm 30/90$]_n laminates could be attributed to two reasons. First, the ductile interleaving film, being strongly bonded to the glass-epoxy layer did in fact suppress delamination growth by crack tip shear-yielding [5]. Reports by Refs.[2] and [3] showed that thermoset interleaves were effective in delaying delamination initiation but not growth. Further investigation on the possible differences in failure modes occurring during free-edge initiation and subsequent growth (away from the edge) would be necessary to explain this inconsistency as it has been [11,5] found that higher ductility thermoplastic films significantly

enhanced the Mode II fracture toughness, G_{IIc} , while thermoset interleaves were more effective in increasing G_{Ic} . The other possible reason is that the growth pattern may be due to interrupted loading in the tensile tests. Ref. [3] reported that a "pop-in" delamination critical size was necessary for growth to occur. In other words, the interrupted loading would essentially cause the 'initiation' of delaminations in other weaker areas if the preinitiated delaminations are small, as observed in the present study. This indicates that interrupted loading may not be a reliable technique for determining the ability of the interleaving film to resist delamination growth.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on limited experimental data on relatively thin [$\pm 30/90_n$], laminates with interleave films, the following conclusions can be made:

1. Interleaving films incorporated at either the 30/-30 or -30/90 interfaces tend to delay transverse cracking even for laminates with $n=2$. Thus, for relatively thick films in thin laminates, the main advantages of interleaving are to reduce stiffness losses due to transverse cracking and increase the onset stress of subsequent local delamination.
2. After delamination onset, the stiffness loss due to delamination growth interleaved laminates does not vary significantly from baseline laminates implying that similar sublaminates were formed. However, the scattered pockets of delamination during incremental testing may be evidence that interleaving suppressed the rate of delamination growth.

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